

A Comparative Experimental Evaluation of an Automated Batchwise and Continuous Operation Mode for Scaling Up a Falling Film Looping Photoreactor

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Abstract

A falling film looping photoreactor was transferred from batch to continuous operation and the practical operability was demonstrated for the light-driven bromination of toluene with the 2×A reactor module (space velocity $s = 15 \text{ min}^{-1}$, reactor volume $V_r = 20 \text{ mL}$, toluene concentration = 500 mM) over 24 h operation under automated batch conditions with a productivity of up to $341.1 \text{ g} \cdot \text{d}^{-1}$ of benzyl bromide. The influence of the external flow rate \dot{V}_{ext} on the residence time distribution (RTD) within the falling film looping photoreactor was evaluated using pulsed tracer experiments. The resulting residence time distribution curves were evaluated by using an axial dispersion model to get deeper insight into the characteristic hydrodynamics within the falling film looping photoreactor during continuous stirred tank reactor (CSTR) operation. Based on this knowledge, a direct transfer from a batch stirred tank reactor (BSTR) to a CSTR was realized with a comparable productivity of up to $363.7 \text{ g} \cdot \text{d}^{-1}$ of benzyl bromide by adjusting the hydrodynamic residence time in the continuous setup to match the conditions in the batch system. With increasing \dot{V}_{ext} ($3.3 - 40 \text{ mL} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$) in CSTR operation of the 2×A reactor module productivities of up to $3045.8 \text{ g} \cdot \text{day}^{-1}$ were determined, with steady state yields between 89.5 - 61.8 %. CSTR operation was also applied to the 4×A reactor module ($V_r = 50 \text{ mL}$), realizing a scaling factor of ≈ 2.4 (ideal scaling factor = 2.5) for the observed productivities for the transfer between the different sized reactor modules.

Introduction

Driven by ongoing economic growth and industrial expansion the global energy consumption is projected to increase by nearly 50 % over the next 30 years and is accompanied by immense greenhouse gas emissions that lead to severe environmental deterioration and climate change. The deployment of renewable and clean energy sources can help to sustain economic growth, while mitigating negative environmental effects.^[1]

In fact, the European union has undertaken major effort to optimize and enhance the renewable energy mix towards energy security and sustainability resulting in a total renewable energy share of 41 % in 2022^[2]. The International Energy Agency projects that renewable power generation will exceed fossil fired power generation by 2025^[3]. Nevertheless, the intermittence of renewables such as solar- and wind power in energy production raises the need for suited energy storage strategies^[4,5]. As the world's top 3 greenhouse gas emitter, chemical industry can be a valuable recipient of renewable energy and therefore majorly contribute to carbon neutrality^[6]. In fact, initiatives of the European union declare a greenhouse gas emission reduction goal of 55 % by 2030^[7], requiring efficient electrification strategies^[8].

In recent years, light-driven reactions have attracted growing attention, reflected by a rapidly increasing number of publications.^[9] Recently, Moschetta et al. conducted a pharmaceutical industry-wide survey on the implementation of photochemical transformations both on the discovery and process development scale. Around 86 % of the surveyed companies own scale up equipment, distributed quite equally between batch and continuous equipment, but only 50 % respond having experience in process development on the kg production scale. In general, a lack of internal know-how regarding photochemistry scale up is one likely reason for less utilization of photochemistry in process chemistry.^[10] Despite the challenging scale-up process of photochemical reactors, grounded mainly in the particularities of photon transport along with efficient heat and mass transport, photochemical transformations are becoming increasingly relevant for industrial application.^[11] To ensure larger-scale production, a recent shift from batch to continuous flow operation is apparent.^[12] Nevertheless, a transfer from a batch photoreactor towards continuous operation is often not possible directly, raising the need for dedicated photoreactor concepts that ensure both scalability and can be operated discontinuously as well as continuously. Recently the direct geometrical scale-up of a falling film looping photoreactor was demonstrated for the light-driven allylic bromination of toluene.^[13] The proposed reactor concepts ensured comparable reaction condition at different scales through ensuring a constant photon-to-reagent ratio.

Visible-light driven halogenations play an increasingly important role in organic synthesis.^[14] N-Bromosuccinimide (NBS) can be activated by light and represents a widely employed reagent in organic chemistry, primarily due to its selective bromination capabilities and mild oxidative properties. It is best known for facilitating allylic and benzylic brominations via a radical mechanism, ensuring controlled bromine release and minimizes polybromination.^[15-18] Benzyl bromide is a versatile benzylating agent in organic synthesis to functionalize alcohols, thiols and amines.^[19-21] It plays a key role in synthesizing pharmaceuticals,^[22,23] in material science for polymer

functionalization,^[24-27] and in the synthesis of quaternary ammonium salts used as ionic liquids, surfactants and phase transfer catalysts.^[28,29]

To make photochemical transformations competitive with current processes, photons must be utilized very efficiently, raising the need for suited reactor design and operation.^[30] In contrast to traditional thermally-driven chemistry, where the energy required for a chemical transformation is supplied as heat, photochemical transformations are driven by the absorption of radiation within the ultraviolet and visible wavelength (UV-vis) range. The absorbed photon not only acts as an energy source but must be considered as a reagent^[31]. In general, the absorbed photon flux determines the rate of photochemical transformations. The scalability of a photochemical reactor is directly related to efficient irradiation of the reaction solution, that, due to the exponential decrease of light intensity with the pathlength of an absorbing medium, will be compromised if a photoreactor is simply scaled by its size^[32]. Pronounced intensity gradients lead to undesired variations in kinetic rates^[33]. In addition to the radiative transport, mass transport (convection and diffusion) influences the rate of a photochemical reaction^[34]. Microstructured flow photoreactors are widely discussed as scalable photoreactor platforms enabling uniform and thorough irradiation of the reaction solution and the possibility of continuous operation^[12,32,34,35]. To maintain the outlined benefits, scale up of microstructured flow photoreactors is limited to numbering up (internal and external) and sizing up in length that can create issues with equal flow distribution, an increased pressure drop and eventually extensive costs^[36]. For the efficient scale up of a photoreactor major scaling factors like, the used light source (emission spectrum and emission geometry), absorption spectra of the used substrates, photoreactor material (transmissivity), reactor geometry, the illuminated reaction surface, light intensity, the distance between light source and reactor, the pathlength, photon stoichiometry, reaction temperature and heat exchange, mixing and flow patterns must be considered^[31,37,38]. The multitude of influencing parameters and their interplay create a high level of complexity during scale up.

To tackle the challenging scale-up, several sophisticated theoretical frameworks and scalable reactor concepts have been published recently. The models developed by Aillet et al.^[39] and Gaulhofer et al.^[40] focus on the impact of mass transport processes in microreactors and a mini-plant photoreactor, respectively. Going one step further, Sezen-Edmonds et al.^[41] and Wiedemann et al.^[42] aim for model-based reactor scale-up strategies by predicting photoreactor performance along different scales and optimizing reaction conditions and transport processes accordingly. In the context of scalable reactors, Lee et al. reported the successful scale-up from gram to kilogram per day using a Taylor-flow vortex reactor, achieving a more than 300-fold increase in productivity while maintaining safe long-term operation^[43]. Li et al. demonstrated that a stirred loop reactor could be scaled for a light-driven hydrogen evolution reaction by more than an order of magnitude, while simultaneously increasing the apparent quantum yield by up to 17-fold through mass transport intensification^[44]. Similarly, Gaulhofer et al. enhanced the performance of a pilot-scale reactor by a factor of 2.4 through the integration of static mixers^[45]. As other scalable alternatives, also laser-driven reactors^[46], spinning disk reactors^[47] or aerosol photoreactors^[48] are discussed in the literature.

Falling film photoreactors (FFP) have been demonstrated as widely applied and easily scalable photoreactor concept in wastewater treatment. Governed by their unique design, thin falling vertical liquid fluid films can be formed that enhance the performance of FFP compared to traditional batch reactors. Due to the thin liquid film formation high surface area-to-volume ratios and reduced reactant diffusion distances can be facilitated, that lead to large reaction surface areas and efficient heat- and mass transfer resulting in high conversion rates, short residence times and improved process control.^[49] Besides the outlined benefits, thin light-absorbing liquid films counteract light attenuation, avoiding strong gradients of the reaction rate that can lead to increased byproduct formation.^[13,33] In this work a modular falling film looping photoreactor (FFLPR)^[13] is used to elaborate scale up strategies for long-term operation. Therefore, automated batch stirred tank reactor (ABSTR) and continuous batch stirred tank reactor (CSTR) operation of the FFLPR at increasing reactor sizes are compared at similar reaction conditions in a feasibility study.

Scale Up Strategies Using the FFLPR

Assuming comparable falling film thicknesses along different FFLPR scales, a direct geometrical scale-up of the irradiated or wetted surface can be applied, while maintaining a constant irradiance over the different reactor scales (see Figure 1 a). In addition to the scalability of the photoreactor itself, the reactor's operating mode can influence the expected productivity and yields. Dependent on the production scale, batch or continuous processing can be more beneficial.^[50]

Figure 1: **a** Schematic depiction of the direct geometrical scale up procedure with an increasing irradiated/wetted surface of a falling film reactor while maintaining the same irradiance over the different reactor scales. **b** Schematic depiction of process scale up for FFLPR operation as ABSTR and CSTR.

The presented FFLPR can be operated both in ABSTR and CSTR operation mode. Figure 1 b demonstrates the basic design concept used to enable both operational modes. The falling film formation is realized by using a peristaltic pump for internal recycling of the reaction solution at a given internal volumetric flow rate (\dot{V}_{int}). An additional external flow, with the external volumetric flow rate (\dot{V}_{ext}), can be applied by two peristaltic pumps. The FFLPR can either be automatically filled, emptied and cleaned in ABSTR mode or operated continuously in CSTR mode. The used peristaltic pumps are controlled and adjusted by a scale-based feedback signal. The CSTR operation of the FFLPR is a distinctive approach that combines looping falling film operation with continuous CSTR

processing, where internal recycling stabilizes the falling film that presents a feature not found in conventional CSTRs.

A general procedure of ABSTR operation consists of a series of individual reaction cycles, interrupted by a fast refilling of the reactor to V_r and cleaning procedure of around 40 s. The number of cycles during a given operational time (t_o) is determined by the reaction time (t_r) chosen for each individual cycle.

For CSTR operation the reactor is initially filled to V_r using the peristaltic pump at the inlet of the reactor, subsequently both peristaltic pumps responsible for the external flow are tuned to a desired \dot{V}_{ext} . Flooding or dry running of the reactor due to slight deviations of the set \dot{V}_{ext} is prevented by comprehensive tuning of the peristaltic pumps based on the weight of the used reactor module. Using Eq. (1) the hydrodynamic mean residence time ($\bar{\tau}_h$) can be calculated and adjusted to t_r to ensure comparable reaction condition between ABSTR and CSTR operation.

$$\bar{\tau}_h = \frac{V_r}{\dot{V}_{ext}} \quad (1)$$

To ensure comparable reaction conditions for FFLPR operation, independent of the reactor scale, similar area-to-volume ratios (AVR) must be ensured. The AVR equals the specific surface area (A_s). A_s can be derived as the ratio of the irradiated (wetted) area (A) and V_r according to Eq. (2).

$$A_s = \frac{A}{V_r} \quad (2)$$

Comparable falling film formation along the different reactor scales was controlled by the space velocity (s) that can be derived from the ratio of \dot{V}_{ext} and V_r using Eq. (3).

$$s = \frac{\dot{V}_{ext}}{V_r} \quad (3)$$

Photoreactions are often limited by the photon flux emitted by a light source (q_{ext}). The normalization of the product amount (n) with respect to time (t) and q_{ext} leads to the external photonic efficiency (ξ_{ext}) defined in equation (4).

$$\xi_{ext} = \frac{\Delta n (product)}{\Delta t} \cdot \frac{1}{q_{ext}} \quad (4)$$

Furthermore, comparable irradiation conditions must be ensured, which can be estimated by the available volumetric photon flux (q_{vol}). q_{vol} can be derived as the ratio between the total available photon flux (q_{ext}) of the used light source and V_r using Eq. (5).

$$q_{vol} = \frac{q_{ext}}{V_r} \quad (5)$$

Normalization of the product amount (n) with respect to V_r and time (t), results in the space-time-yield (STY) as performance indicator shown in Eq. (6).

$$STY = \frac{\Delta n (product)}{\Delta t \cdot V_r} \quad (6)$$

Based on the obtained benzyl bromide (BBr, product) mass (m_{BBr}), the daily BBr productivity (Q_{BBr}) can be calculated using the Eq. (7).

$$Q_{BBr} = \frac{m_{BBr}}{t_o} \cdot 24 \text{ h} \quad (7)$$

Results and Discussion

Batch Stirred Tank Reactor Operation

To enable a comprehensive comparison between ABSTR and CSTR performance, different operation modes of the FFLPR were studied using the *N*-bromosuccinimide (NBS) induced light-driven allylic bromination of toluene in acetonitrile as benchmark reaction. Starting conditions were set to the $V_r = 10$ mL scale at a toluene concentration $c_{tol} = 500$ mM (0.46 g) using the 1×A module ($s = 15$ min⁻¹, $q = 46$ μmol · s⁻¹, $q_{vol} = 4.62$ μmol s⁻¹ · mL⁻¹, $A_s = 785$ m² · m⁻³) as initial benchmark conditions for the elaboration of suited ABSTR and CSTR operational conditions. The reaction performance was studied using batch operation (Batch Stirred Tank Reactor (BSTR) operation) of the FFLPR over 12 min (sampling interval: 2 min) and evaluated using the yield, obtained product mass m_{BBR} and corresponding space-time yields (*STY*) as performance metrics.

In a first process optimization attempt on the $V_r = 10$ mL scale, c_{tol} was increased to 815 mM (0.75 g), based on the maximal solubility of NBS in the reaction mixture to ensure operation under homogeneous reaction conditions. For both concentrations high product yields of ≈ 90 % (see Figure 2 a) were observed, being in good agreement with previously published results^[13]. A comparison of the obtained m_{BBR} (see Figure 2 b) reveals an increase of m_{BBR} by 56.7 % from 0.74 g to 1.30 g after 12 min. At $c_{tol} = 500$ mM, maximal yields can be observed already at t_r of 4 min ($m_{BBR} = 0.75$ g) compared to 8 min at $c_{tol} = 800$ mM ($m_{BBR} = 1.28$ g), which would allow for a shortening of t_r by 50 % for ABSTR operation, eventually resulting in twice as many reaction cycles that can be realized during ABSTR operation. Hence, t_r optimized ABSTR operation would result in a similar P_{BBR} independent of c_{tol} . An evaluation of the calculated *STY* depicted in Figure 2 c reveals a maximal *STY* at 4 min for both evaluated concentrations. Therefore, both 500 mM and 815 mM c_{tol} at different t_r are

Figure 2: a Comparison of 500 mM and 815 mM substrate concentrations for the allylic bromination of toluene regarding a the relative and b m_{BBR} and c *STY* in the 1×A module.

potentially suited for ABSTR operation.

The influence of $s = 15$ min⁻¹, $s = 7.5$ min⁻¹ (minimal s for stable falling film formation), and operation without falling film, i.e. just applying active stirring of the reaction solution filled into reactor reservoir (referred to as a $s = 0$ min⁻¹) was performed at $V_r = 20$ mL for $c_{tol} = 500$ mM (0.92 g) and $c_{tol} = 815$ mM (1.50 g) using the 1×A module ($q_{ext} = 46$ μmol · s⁻¹, $q_{vol} = 2.31$ μmol · s⁻¹ · mL⁻¹, $A_s = 392.5$ m² · m⁻³).

Even though q_{vol} and A_s decreased by 50 % due to the increase in V_r from 10 mL to 20 mL, an increase of the product mass after reaction ($t = 12$ min) by a factor ≈ 2 (compared to a V_r of 10 mL) for both c_{tol} of 500 mM and 815 mM can be observed when falling film operation is applied (see Figure 3 a and c). At a concentration of 815 mM without looping operation a decrease of m_{BBR} by ≈ 11 % can be observed (see Figure 3 c). Even at high $s = 15 \text{ min}^{-1}$ the time needed for maximal yields shift from 4 min to 6 min for a concentration of 500 mM and from 8 to 10 min for a concentration of 815 mM (see Figure 3 a and c), compared to a V_r of 10 mL (see Figure 1 a and b). A reduction of $s = 15 \text{ min}^{-1}$ to $s = 0 \text{ min}^{-1}$ (operation without internal looping/falling film) leads to a decrease of the STY for a 500 mM and 815 mM concentration by ≈ 48.9 % and ≈ 56.2 % respectively (see Figure 3 b and d). At a concentration of 815 mM, the maximum STY shifts towards higher t_r at $s < 15 \text{ min}^{-1}$ (see Figure 3 d). In summary, severe effects of s on the t_r and STY can be observed for both examined concentrations. The negative influence of insufficient mixing observable for low space velocities or stopped falling film operation gets more pronounced at high substrate concentrations, showcasing

Figure 3: Comparison of the influence of different space velocities on the allylic bromination of toluene at a V_r of 20 mL. a and b m_{BBR} and STY for 500 mM. c and d m_{BBR} and STY for 815 mM in the 1×A module.

the importance of the space velocity for the assessment of suited reaction cycle planning for ABSTR operation.

Residence time Distribution

Figure 4: a)-e) Comparison of the experimental residence time density distribution and simulations based on an axial dispersion model for increasing \dot{V}_{ext} using the 2×A module. f) Comparison of the simulated residence time density functions.

As basis for transferring the results obtained for batch operation to continuous operation, the residence time distribution (RTD) behavior in the falling film loop reactor was investigated through pulsed tracer experiments using the 2×A module and \dot{V}_{ext} ranging from 3.3 - 40 mL min⁻¹. To quantify the deviation from ideal flow, an axial dispersion model with closed-closed boundary conditions^[51] was applied to determine the Bodenstein number Bo, which represents the ratio of convective- and dispersive flow in the reactor.

In Figure 4 the resulting simulated RTD density functions $E_{sim}(t)$ and the estimated Bo-numbers are shown for an increasing \dot{V}_{ext} and compared to the experimental RTD functions $E_{exp}(t)$. The simulation results are in good agreement with the experimental data. The determined Bo-numbers between 0.4 and 1.1 indicate strong axial dispersion and significant backmixing resulting in a pronounced deviation from ideal plug flow behavior, for which $Bo \geq 100$ is often considered as the critical value^[51]. To gain additional insights into the hydrodynamic behavior, the mean residence time $\bar{\tau}$ was determined from the measured residence time density function, and compared to $\bar{\tau}_h$ calculated by Eq. (1). As shown in Figure 5, $\bar{\tau}$ is smaller than $\bar{\tau}_h$ for \dot{V}_{ext} below 10 mL min⁻¹, and $\bar{\tau}$ exceeds $\bar{\tau}_h$ for \dot{V}_{ext} above 10 mL min⁻¹.

Figure 5: Experimental mean residence time, hydrodynamic residence time and Bodenstein number as a function of \dot{V}_{ext} using the 2×A module.

At \dot{V}_{ext} below 10 mL min^{-1} , the reduced residence time suggests incomplete wetting and dry spot formation, as also reported in several studies^[52-54]. These phenomena result in a reduced wetted surface area, bypassing of the liquid through preferred rivulets, and channeling, all leading to an increased overall liquid velocity^[52,55]. Conversely, the increased residence time at above 10 mL min^{-1} suggests the increasing impact of retentive mechanisms such as fluid recirculation near the inlet or outlet zones^[56,57] or wave formation within the reactor^[57]. In addition, surface roughness may contribute to flow retardation by increasing resistance along the flow path^[58].

ABSTR Operation

As a proof of concept (PoC) for long term ABSTR operation, serial batch experiments over 24 h in the 2×A module ($s = 15 \text{ min}^{-1}$, $q_{ext} = 102 \mu\text{mol} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$, $q_{vol} = 5.10 \mu\text{mol} \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \cdot \text{mL}^{-1}$, $A_s = 894.9 \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{m}^{-3}$) were conducted using a V_r of 20 mL $c_{tol} = 500 \text{ mM}$, (0.92 g) and $c_{tol} = 815 \text{ mM}$, (1.50 g) and t_r of 10 min and 12 min (cycle times 10.6 min and 12.6 min).

The 2×A module was applied to increase the overall absorbable photon flux. To adjust both q_{vol} and A_s , towards the initial benchmark conditions, V_r was chosen based on the minimal volume needed to ensure stable falling film operation of the reactor module. m_{BBr} of 226.6 g and 307.8 g were registered by high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) after 24 h operation at concentrations (see Figure 6 a), respectively. This corresponds well to the isolated product yields of 226.5 g and 311.2 g (see Table 13 SI). Average STY of $766.7 \mu\text{mol} \cdot (\text{L} \cdot \text{s})^{-1}$ and $1041.4 \mu\text{mol} \cdot (\text{L} \cdot \text{s})^{-1}$ can be reported (see Figure 6 b). A comparison to the STY with the benchmark experiment used for process optimization (see Figure 2 c) at a t_r of 10 min and 12 min ($c_{tol} = 500 \text{ mM}$ and $c_{tol} = 815 \text{ mM}$, respectively) gives STY of $700.0 \mu\text{mol} \cdot (\text{L} \cdot \text{s})^{-1}$ and $1052.7 \mu\text{mol} \cdot (\text{L} \cdot \text{s})^{-1}$ being in good agreement with the calculated average STY for ABSTR operation. This showcases the transferability of findings

from experiments conducted in the 1×A to the 2×A module if the given reaction conditions are comparable.

Figure 6: **a** Obtained m_{BBr} and **b** STY for 500 mM and 815 mM ABSTR operation over 24 h at t_r of 10 min and 12 min using the 2×A module.

To further improve the STY for ABSTR operation, 1 h production of BBr at t_r of 6 min and 8 min was investigated using the conditions applied in the PoC experiment. The examined t_r were chosen based on the time derived from the benchmark experiment where no further increase of the obtained product mass with respect to the t_r could be observed (see Figure 2 b). Average STY of $1154.2 \mu mol \cdot (L \cdot s)^{-1}$ and $1426.3 \mu mol \cdot (L \cdot s)^{-1}$ were calculated for, respectively (see Figure 7 b). A comparison to the STY of the benchmark experiment used for process optimization (see Figure 2 c) at a t_r of 6 min and 8 min (500 mM and 815 mM) gives STY of $1333.3 \mu mol \cdot (L \cdot s)^{-1}$ and $1545.1 \mu mol \cdot (L \cdot s)^{-1}$ being in good agreement with the calculated average STY for ABSTR operation. This corresponds to a respective increase of the STY by $\approx 50.5\%$ ($c_{tol} = 500$ mM) and $\approx 37.0\%$ ($c_{tol} = 815$ mM) compared to ABSTR t_r of 10 min and 12 min. Extrapolation of the obtained absolute product yields from an operation time of 1 h to 24 h results in $Q_{BBr} = 341.1 g \cdot day^{-1}$ and $Q_{BBr} = 421.5 g \cdot day^{-1}$ for t_r of 6 min and 8 min.

Figure 7: **a** Obtained m_{BBr} and **b** STY for 500 mM and 815 mM ABSTR operation over 1 h at t_r of 6 min and 8 min using the 2×A module.

Figure 8 **a** Obtained m_{BBR} and **b** STY for 500 mM ABSTR operation over 1 h at t_r of 6 min using the 4x4 module.

ABSTR operation for 1 h was scaled by increasing V_r by a factor of 2.5 from 20 mL to 50 mL at $c_{tol} = 500$ mM (2.3 g) per cycle of operation ($t_r = 6$ min, time per operation cycle = 6.6 min). The reaction was carried out in the 4x4 module ($s = 15$ min⁻¹, $q_{ext} = 184.60$ $\mu\text{mol} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$, $q_{vol} = 3.69$ $\mu\text{mol} \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \cdot \text{mL}^{-1}$, $A_s = 628.0$ m² · m⁻³). V_r was chosen based on the minimal volume needed to ensure stable falling film operation of the reactor module, requiring operation with lower q_{vol} and A_s in comparison to the reactions carried out in the 2x4 module. Nevertheless, for the 4x4 module average STY of 1062.5 $\mu\text{mol} \cdot (\text{L} \cdot \text{s})^{-1}$ (see Figure 8 **b**) could be achieved, comparable to ABSTR operation of the 2x4 module with an average STY of 1154.2 $\mu\text{mol} \cdot (\text{L} \cdot \text{s})^{-1}$ (see Figure 7 **b**). Governed by the 2.5 factor increase of the V_r under identical reaction conditions along the different reactor scales, a theoretical $Q_{BBR} = 852.8$ g · day⁻¹ was calculated. Using the obtained $m_{BBR} = 32.7$ g after 1 h of operation (see Figure 8 **a**), $Q_{BBR} = 785.0$ g · day⁻¹ was determined corresponding to only a slight deviation of ≈ 7.9 %, in comparison to the ideal case (scaling factor obtained ≈ 2.36 ; ideal scaling factor = 2.5).

CSTR Operation

Figure 9: Relative Yields with respect to operation time observed at different \dot{V}_{ext} at a fixed s of 15 min^{-1} using the 2xA and 4xA module.

CSTR operation at a scale of V_r of 20 mL, $c_{tol} = 500 \text{ mM}$, (0.92 g) in the 2xA module ($s = 15 \text{ min}^{-1}$, $q_{ext} = 102 \mu\text{mol} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$, $q_{vol} = 5.10 \mu\text{mol} \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \cdot \text{mL}^{-1}$, $A_s = 894.9 \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{m}^{-3}$) for one 1 h was tested for \dot{V}_{ext} of 3.3, 5, 10, 20 and 40 $\text{mL} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$, corresponding to $\bar{\tau}_h$ of 6, 4, 2, 1, 0.5 min. The reaction times for t_r CSTR operation were defined by aligned the $\bar{\tau}_h$ defined in Eq. (1) to the t_r for ABSTR operation. V_r was set to $\approx 20 \text{ mL}$ and maintained by slight automatic \dot{V}_{ext} adjustments of peristaltic pumps using a scale to prevent reactor flooding or dry running.

In addition, CSTR operation for 1 h was scaled to $V_r \approx 50 \text{ mL}$, $c_{tol} = 500 \text{ mM}$, (2.3 g) in the 4xA module ($s = 15 \text{ min}^{-1}$, $q_{ext} = 184.60 \mu\text{mol} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$, $q_{vol} = 3.69 \mu\text{mol} \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \cdot \text{mL}^{-1}$, $A_s = 628.0 \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{m}^{-3}$) for which \dot{V}_{ext} of $12.5 \text{ mL} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$ corresponding to a $\bar{\tau}_h$ of 4 min (max. STY). For all examined \dot{V}_{ext} and reactor modules a stabilization of the Y could be observed after an induction period of 10 min for CSTR operation (see Figure 9). For the calculation of Q_{BBR} the average of the measured relative yields for $t > 10 \text{ min}$ was used to calculate the average steady state yield (SSY).

Dependent on the applied \dot{V}_{ext} , a decrease of SSY from 89.5 % to 61.8 % can be observed (see Figure 10 b). Interestingly, the observed change of the SSY does not correlate in a linear fashion with the decreasing $\bar{\tau}_h$ within the reactor, indicating that CSTR operation of the FFLPR is outside of the photon limited reaction regime. Increasing \dot{V}_{ext} from $3.3 \text{ mL} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$ to $40 \text{ mL} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$ leads to a reduction of the hydrodynamic residence time from 6 min to 0.5 min. Under photonically limited reaction conditions this would correlate to drop of the expected SSY from 89.5 % to a value of $\approx 7.5 \%$. Furthermore, an increase of the calculated Q_{BBR} by more than a factor of 8 can be observed while increasing the external \dot{V}_{ext} of $3.3 \text{ mL} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$ ($Q_{BBR} = 363.7 \text{ g} \cdot \text{day}^{-1}$) to $40 \text{ mL} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$ ($Q_{BBR} = 3045.8 \text{ g} \cdot \text{day}^{-1}$) (see Figure 10 a).

Comparing the CSTR performance between the 2xA and the 4xA at the same hydrodynamic residence time of 4 min (max. STY) at the corresponding \dot{V}_{ext} of $5 \text{ mL} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$ and $12.5 \text{ mL} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$ (see Figure 10 a,

Figure 10: **a** Q_{BBR} for CSTR operation of the FFLPR for 1 h at different \dot{V}_{ext} . **b** Steady state yields of the CSTR at different \dot{V}_{ext} using the 2x and 4x module.

green and yellow column), an increase of the productivity from $Q_{BBR} = 545.9 \text{ g} \cdot \text{day}^{-1}$ to $Q_{BBR} = 1290.5 \text{ g} \cdot \text{day}^{-1}$ can be observed. This aligns well with the expected increase in productivity, assuming a comparable STY for the 2x and 4x reactor scales determined from the ABSTR experiments (see Figure 7 b and Figure 8 b). This finding also aligns well the observed stable SSY of 88.7 % and 83.8 % between the 2x and 4x reactor scale (see Figure 10 b, green and yellow column).

A comparison of ABSTR and CSTR experiments is depicted Table 1. Q_{BBR} of the ABSTR was increased by $\approx 50.6 \%$ and $\approx 35.5 \%$ (500 mM and 815 mM) for the 2x module by systematic adjustments of the applied t_r for each individual cycle of ABSTR operation. Long-term ABSTR operation could be demonstrated over operational times of 24 h. ABSTR operation could be successfully transferred between the 2x and 4x module while maintaining comparable STY for a given t_r . This enabled an increase of Q_{BBR} from $226.5 \text{ g} \cdot \text{day}^{-1}$ (2x, 500 mM) to $785.0 \text{ g} \cdot \text{day}^{-1}$ (4x, 500 mM), corresponding to an increase by a factor of ≈ 3.5 . CSTR operation at different \dot{V}_{ext} ranging from 3.3 to $40 \text{ mL} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$ ($\bar{\tau}_h$: 6 - 0.5 min) using the 2x module led to an increase of Q_{BBR} from $363.7 \text{ g} \cdot \text{day}^{-1}$ to $3045.8 \text{ g} \cdot \text{day}^{-1}$, while maintaining reasonable SSY between 89.5 - 61.8 %. For CSTR operation at $12.5 \text{ mL} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$ ($\bar{\tau}_h$ at max STY of 4 min) using the 4x module, Q_{BBR} of $1290.5 \text{ g} \cdot \text{day}^{-1}$ at high yields of 83.8 % were demonstrated. Comparing ABSTR to CSTR operation (see Table 1) shows that CSTR operation is clearly superior regarding the achievable productivities. For ABSTR operation a t_r of 6 min (see Figure 2 a) is needed to reach maximal product yields for each individual batch cycle. In contrast to this for CSTR operation a stable SSY can be maintained even at high \dot{V}_{ext} corresponding to short $\bar{\tau}_h$ (see Figure 9) resulting in significantly increased Q_{BBR} . Considering the demonstrated comparable STY between the different reactor scales at a given $\bar{\tau}_h$ or t_r , a scaling factor of ≈ 2.36 for CSTR operation between the 2x module ($5 \text{ mL} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$, $\bar{\tau}_h = 4 \text{ min}$) and 4x module ($12.5 \text{ mL} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$, $\bar{\tau}_h = 4 \text{ min}$) (see Figure 10) is estimated. Applying this factor to the CSTR operation, 4x module ($100 \text{ mL} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$, $\bar{\tau}_h = 0.5 \text{ min}$) would result in an expected $Q_{BBR} \approx 7199 \text{ g} \cdot \text{day}^{-1}$.

Table 1: Comparison of Q_{BBr} for ABSTR and CSTR operation for using the FFLPR with the 2×A and 4×A module as function of on the applied reaction conditions.

mode	module	c_{tol} / mmol · L ⁻¹	t_0 / h	t_r / min	V_r / mL	A_s / m ² · m ⁻³	q_{vol} / μmol · (mL s) ⁻¹	Q_{BBr} / g · day ⁻¹
ABSTR	2×A	500	24	10	20	894.9	5.1	226.5
	2×A	500	1	6	20	894.9	5.1	341.1
	4×A	500	1	6	50	628	3.69	785.0
	2×A	815	24	12	20	894.9	5.1	311.1
	2×A	815	1	8	20	894.9	5.1	421.5
CSTR	4×A	500	1	4	50	628	3.69	1290.5
	2×A	500	1	6	20	894.9	5.1	363.7
	2×A	500	1	4	20	894.9	5.1	545.9
	2×A	500	1	2	20	894.9	5.1	909.2
	2×A	500	1	1	20	894.9	5.1	1678.9
	2×A	500	1	0.5	20	894.9	5.1	3045.8

NBS mediated light-driven allylic bromination of various compounds under continuous flow has been demonstrated in literature. To enable comparability to the FFLPR with literature examples q_{ext} was accessed using literature data on the irradiation characteristics 365 nm LEDs^[59,60] and blacklight CFL^[61], detailed information on the photonic evaluation is supplied in section 6 ESI. of Using a diagonal photoflow reactor (LX-1, MiChS) under UV LED irradiation (365 ± 5 nm, UV-LED-S MiChS, 360 W, $\eta \approx 27-30\%$ ^[62,63], $q_{ext} \approx 329.10-365.56 \mu\text{mol} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$, $\xi_{ext} \approx 0.048-0.043$) productivities of Q_{BBr} of $9.73 \text{ g} \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$ was achieved.^[64] Allylic bromination of toluene using a capillary reactor (blacklight CFL, 25 W, $\eta \approx 8-11\%$, $q_{ext} \approx 6.6-9.20 \mu\text{mol} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$, $\xi_{ext} \approx 0.46-0.33$) was demonstrated with Q_{BBr} of $\approx 1.89 \text{ g} \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$.^[65] The FFLPR showed superior performance under CSTR operation of the 2×A module (40 mL min⁻¹) with $Q_{BBr} = 94 \text{ g} \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$.

Conclusions and Outlook

The operation of the FFLPR could be successfully transferred towards ABSTR and CSTR operation. Based on the stable long-term operation of the CSTR at constant SSY , high Q_{BBR} were achieved compared to ABSTR operation. The high Q_{BBR} found for CSTR operation at high \dot{V}_{ext} , corresponding to low $\bar{\tau}_h$ and $\bar{\tau}$, indicate CSTR operation outside of the photon limited reaction regime. This is also reflected in the calculated ξ_{ext} for CSTR operation ($2 \times A$ module, 40 mL min^{-1} , $Q_{BBR} = 3045.8 \text{ g} \cdot \text{day}^{-1}$) of ≈ 2 , which is in principle possible due a radical propagation after the light-induced activation of NBS.^[66,67] This also means that photons are used more efficiently, which translates into potential cost savings during operation of the CSTR. Stable and comparable STY along the different sized FFLPR modules finally resulted in a scale up factor ≈ 2.4 (ideal scaling factor = 2.5) between the $2 \times A$ and $4 \times A$ reactor module indicating comparable reaction conditions with increasing module size. With this scale up factor to the $4 \times A$ module operated at \dot{V}_{ext} of 100 mL min^{-1} yields and estimated $Q_{BBR} \approx 7199 \text{ g} \cdot \text{day}^{-1}$. In addition to the application of higher \dot{V}_{ext} to increase the throughput in a flow photoreactor, parallelization of multiple reactors (numbering-up) is a promising and widely discussed scale-up strategy in flow photochemistry.^[36,68–71] Even though a further scale-up of a single FFLPR is potentially possible as outlined by existing commercially available pilot plant FFP with inner diameters of up to 50 cm,^[72] numbering-up of FFLPR modules with V_r in the double digit mL scale offers benefits of increased process safety thus making the numbering-up approach of medium size FFLPR modules a versatile strategy for the potential application of CSTR FFLPR modules on a technical production scale.

Materials and Methods

Chemicals and Instruments

All commercially available reagents and solvents were purchased from companies as follows: water: Milli-Q, toluene: SRL, HPLC grade acetonitrile: Merck, N-Bromosuccinimide: SRL, Ethyl acetate: SRL, Hexane: SRL, Methylene blue: SRL, Ammonium acetate buffer: SRL. Reagents were used directly without purification. Thin layer chromatography (TLC) was performed on Merck silica gel 60 F254.

The BBr yield was determined by HPLC measurements on an Agilent 1260 Infinity II equipped with a C18 column size: 100 × 3.2 mm, 5 μm. An acetonitrile / 5 mM ammonium acetate buffer (80 mL / 20 mL) was used as mobile phase. A \dot{V} of 1 mL min⁻¹ was applied for the HPLC. The reaction mixture was analyzed using a DAD-UV detector at 230 nm. The HPLC instrument facility was availed from NIPER Hajipur. Peristaltic pumps KHM-SW3S40 were used for looping operations and where higher flow rate was required. Peristaltic pumps NKP-DC-S04D were used when lower \dot{V}_{ext} was required. Silicon tubes of various internal diameters were purchased from Kamoer.

Table 2: List of equipment and materials used in the experimental setup, including silicon tubing of various dimensions, peristaltic pump models, custom-made reactor modules and RTD cells, as well as analytical instruments like HPLC and UV-VIS spectrophotometer.

Equipment	Model	Suppliers
(1) silicon tubes	1) ID: 3 mm OD: 5 mm	Kamoer
	2) ID: 2 mm OD: 4 mm	
	3) ID: 1 mm OD: 3.3 mm	
	4) ID: 0.5 mm OD: 2 mm	
	5) ID: 4 mm OD: 6 mm	
(2) peristaltic pump	1) KHM-SW3S40	Kamoer
	2) NKP-DC-S04D	
(3) reactor modules	1) 1×A	custom made ^[13]
	2) 2×A	
	3) 4×A	
(4) RTD cells	ID: 1 mm OD: 3.3 mm	custom made, see section 5 ESI
(5) HPLC	1260 Infinity II	Agilent
(6) UV-VIS spectrophotometer	UV-1780	Shimadzu

Visible Light-Driven Allylic Bromination of Toluene

The allylic bromination of toluene was performed under visible-light LED irradiation in a FFLPR operated as ABSTR and CSTR using acetonitrile as solvent. Two substrate concentrations were studied in 20 mL batches within a 2×A reactor module: 500 mM (920 mg toluene, 1869 mg NBS) and 815 mM (1500 mg toluene, 3046.5 mg NBS). Optimization used half-sized 10 mL batches in the 1×A module (46 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ photon flux, $s = 15 \text{ min}^{-1}$). Reactor modules (1×A, 2×A, and 4×A) enabled reactions with reaction volumes of 10, 20, and 50 mL, irradiated with photon fluxes of 46, 102, and 185 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$, respectively^[13]. In CSTR mode, reactor volume was precisely controlled by alternating inlet and outlet pumps (see Figure 1 and 2 ESI) while maintaining continuous looping at a set s . In ABSTR mode, automated pump cycles sequentially manage filling, irradiation, product discharge, washing, and drainage for reproducible batch operation. Reaction progress and yields were determined by HPLC. UV-vis spectrophotometry complemented kinetic measurements by monitoring toluene at 254 nm and benzyl bromide at 230 nm after dilution (see section 2.3 ESI).

Four peristaltic pumps were used in ABSTR experiments: three Kamoer NKP-DC-S04D models for low \dot{V}_{int} with 2 mm ID and 4 mm OD silicone tubing, and one Kamoer KHM-SW3S40 pump for high \dot{V}_{int} looping with 4 mm ID and 6 mm OD tubing. CSTR setups employed three pumps: NKP-DC-S04D models paired with tubing ranging from 0.5 to 3 mm ID for flows of 3.3 to 20 mL \cdot min⁻¹, and KHM-SW3S40 pumps with 4 mm ID tubing for flows above 20 mL \cdot min⁻¹. This arrangement ensured precise and stable flow control across all reaction conditions. Detailed setup and experimental details are provided in section 1 and 2 ESI.

Residence Time Distribution Measurements (RTD)

RTD measurements were conducted using the 2×A module and \dot{V}_{ext} of 3.3 mL min⁻¹, 5.0 mL min⁻¹, 10.0 mL min⁻¹, 20.0 mL min⁻¹ and 40 mL min⁻¹ at a fixed s for internal recycling of 15 min⁻¹. A 500 mL acetonitrile reservoir supplied solvent through the inlet pump, which delivered feed along the reactor wall, while a looping pump ensured internal mixing. Inlet and outlet pumps operated in synchronization, with reactor holdup tightly regulated between 18.4 g and 19.0 g via closed-loop feedback control. For tracer studies, 0.3 mL of 1 g \cdot L⁻¹ methylene blue in acetonitrile was injected using a 0.5 mL syringe into the inlet silicone tubing (1 mm ID, 3.3 mm OD), allowing tracer detection across the reactor inlet and outlet streams. Monitoring continued until signal stabilization confirmed completion of the pulse response.

A detailed description of the used procedure and a user's guide for the RTD cell and measurement software operation can be found the corresponding GitHub repository <https://github.com/photonZfeed/FallingFilmLoopingPhotoreactor>.

Residence Time Distribution Modelling

To gain additional insight into the reactor hydrodynamics, the axial dispersion model in Eq. (8) is solved and the resulting simulated residence time density function is fitted to the measured data^[51]. The tracer injection is approximated as an ideal Dirac pulse.

$$\bar{\tau} \frac{dc_T}{dt} = \frac{1}{Bo} \frac{d^2 c_T}{d\zeta^2} - \frac{dc_T}{d\zeta} \quad (8)$$

c_T represents the tracer concentration at time t and dimensionless length ζ . The time of tracer injection is set as $t = 0$. Bo is the Bodenstein number defined by Eq. (9). u is the liquid velocity, L the length of the liquid film, and D_{ax} the axial dispersion coefficient.

$$Bo = \frac{uL}{D_{ax}} \quad (9)$$

The mean residence time $\bar{\tau}$ is calculated as the first moment of the experimental residence time density distribution $E_{exp}(t)$.

$$\bar{\tau} = \int_0^{\infty} t \cdot E_{exp}(t) dt \quad (10)$$

To solve Eq. (8), the closed-closed boundary conditions proposed by Danckwerts in Eqs. (11) and (12) are used, along with the initial condition in Eq. (7)^[73,74].

$$\zeta = 0: \quad c_{T,in} = c_T - \frac{1}{Bo} \frac{dc_T}{d\zeta} \quad (11)$$

$$\zeta = 1: \quad \frac{dc_T}{d\zeta} = 0 \quad (12)$$

$$t = 0: \quad c_T = 0 \quad (13)$$

The simulated experimental residence time density distribution $E_{sim}(t)$ is determined by Eq. (14). The details on the implementation of the model in Python are summarized in the Github repository related to this work, <https://github.com/photonZfeed/FallingFilmLoopingPhotoreactor>.

$$E_{sim}(t) = \frac{c_T(t, \zeta = 1)}{\int_0^{\infty} c_{T,in}(t) dt} \quad (14)$$

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